

Study of Interaction of Metal(II) Ions with Isoprenaline in Aqueous Solution

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Interaction of isoprenaline, a vasopressor drug, with metal(II) ions in aqueous solution has been investigated potentiometrically using Irving-Rossotti technique. Stepwise and overall stability constants and the thermodynamic parameters have been determined at three different temperatures and at 0.1 M (KCl) ionic strength. Analytical data, IR and potentiometric studies indicate that in the isolated adducts metal ions are attached to the drug through the phenolic hydroxyl groups forming a five-membered ring. Isoprenaline acts on β -receptors, present in heart (β_1 -receptors) and bronchi (β_2 -receptors) on the cell surface. The activity of the drug is catalysed with the formation of Ca^{II} -bridge mixed complex of the drug with the enzyme adenylyl cyclase.

ISOPRENALINE (Aludrin) is 1-(3-4 dihydroxyphenyl)-1-hydroxy-2-(isopropylamino)ethane. After administration of isoprenaline there occur only slight changes in blood pressure and blood sugar. It is more potent against asthma than adrenaline. Although metal complexes of adrenaline and noradrenaline have been studied¹, no study has been made on the reaction of isoprenaline with metal(II) ions. As the major biologically active ions belong to metal(II) group, hence, in continuation of our studies on the interaction of catechol amines²⁻⁴ with metallic ions, we report here the studies on metal(II) isoprenaline systems in aqueous solution.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of high purity. Isoprenaline was obtained from Burroughs Wellcome Ltd. (India). The preparation and standardisation of isoprenaline solution were done as described earlier⁴. The standardisation of the metal ion solutions and the other experimental details were the same as reported earlier⁴.

The value of $\bar{n}H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by Irving-Rossotti equations⁵ from the shifts in the pH-titration curves of the acid, the ligand and the metal solutions⁶. The values of the formation constants were directly obtained from the formation curves and refined by the best least-square fits. The thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH , and ΔS were calculated using the isotherm, isobar and Gibbs-Helmholtz equations, respectively, at 25° and ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl (Table 1).

The metal adducts of the drug were isolated from the aqueous solution and their composition was ascertained by the methods described earlier⁴. The analytical data and the characteristic IR bands (recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer) are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: Conductometric and pH-titrations indicate formation of only two complexes, ML and ML_2 with liberation of only one proton during addition of each molecule of the ligand as shown earlier in case of the corresponding adrenaline⁸, noradrenaline⁹ and dopamine⁶ systems. Further, the analysis of the formation curves indicates that the addition of the ligand molecule to the metal ions follows the same pattern as found for the amino acids⁷ or the other catecholamines³⁻⁴, i.e. the formation of the two complexes is independent of each other. The maximum values of $\bar{n}$ (< 1.8) also confirm formation of only ML and ML_2 complexes in these systems.

Stability constants and thermodynamic parameters: Comparison of the formation constants (Table 1) gives the normal sequence of stability⁸ for these complexes, i.e. $\text{Be} > \text{Mg} > \text{Ca} > \text{Sr} = \text{Ba}$, which is in accordance with the values of ionisation potential and e^2/r ratio of these metal ions. The values of thermodynamic parameters (Table 1) show that the interaction of isoprenaline with metal(II) ions is enthalpy characterised (except for Be^{II}), as the values of entropy change are negative in case of all the metals except Be. The high negative values of enthalpy indicate considerable degree of covalence in metal to ligand bond, while negative values of entropy change show decrease in the number of particles during complex formation. The positive value of entropy in case of Be^{II} probably indicates that complete chelation extensively alters solvation of the various species.

Composition and structure: The analytical data (Table 2) of the isolated complexes give $ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ composition to these adducts, where $M = \text{metal(II)}$ and $L = \text{monovalent negative ion of isoprenaline}$. The important IR bands of the isolated complexes indicate the chelation to take place through the phenolic

TABLE 1—FORMATION AND THERMODYNAMIC DATA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Metal ion	Temp. °C	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	Free energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)			Enthalpy (kcal mol ⁻¹)			Entropy (cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		
					$-\Delta G_1$	$-\Delta G_2$	$-\Delta G$	$-\Delta H_1$	$-\Delta H_2$	$-\Delta H$	ΔS_1	ΔS_2	ΔS
Be ^{II}	0	8.40	5.22	18.62									
	25	8.25	5.20	18.45	11.92	7.14	18.27	2.28	0.29	3.96	30.52	22.96	47.96
	37	7.40	5.00	12.40									
Mg ^{II}	0	5.02	2.26	7.28									
	25	4.55	2.17	6.72	6.25	3.00	8.65	7.00	1.31	18.40	-2.52	5.61	-15.94
	37	4.10	2.15	6.25									
Ca ^{II}	0	4.80	1.95	6.25									
	25	4.05	1.72	5.77	5.55	2.37	7.14	3.72	3.35	7.44	6.17	-3.29	-1.02
	37	3.55	1.60	5.18									
Sr ^{II}	0	3.95	1.65	5.60									
	25	3.70	1.50	4.80	5.08	2.06	6.60	3.72	2.23	5.95	6.57	-0.58	2.13
	37	3.20	1.45	4.65									
Ba ^{II}	0	3.78	1.80	5.00									
	25	3.42	1.10	4.42	4.70	1.51	6.00	4.16	3.00	1.84	1.70	-4.93	15.54
	37	2.95	1.00	3.95									

 TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			$\nu_{\text{NH/OH}}$	δ_{NH} (sec)	δ_{OH}	Coord. - H ₂ O
		N	M	H ₂ O				
Ligand	—	—	—	—	3.600m, 3.860s, 3.240vs	1.630m, 825m	1.950m, 1.290s, 1.250s, 1.120vs	—
Be(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N) ₂ ^a	Yellowish brown	6.50 (6.53)	2.07 (2.09)	—	3.680- 3.240br, 3.600m, 3.400vs, 3.310vs	1.630w, 825m	1.960w, 1.280m, 1.300m, 1.220s, 1.060s	—
Mg(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N) ₂ .2H ₂ O ^a	Reddish brown	5.79 (5.83)	4.96 (5.00)	7.46 (7.50)	3.600- 3.020br, 3.480m, 3.240m	1.630w, 830s	1.960m, 1.320s, 1.240m, 1.060m	3.480m, 3.240m, 1.595m, 870vs
Sr(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N) ₂ .2H ₂ O ^a	Pinkish brown	5.01 (5.15)	15.99 (16.13)	7.19 (7.26)	3.540- 3.040br, 3.520vs	1.630s, 825m	1.955m, 1.320s, 1.240m, 1.030m	3.520vs, 1.600m, 870m

^aHygroscopic, soluble in water and ethanol, and decomposes before melting.

hydroxyl group forming a five-membered ring, confirming the structure reported earlier⁵.

Biological activity : Isoprenaline forms a strong Ca^{II}-bridged mixed complex with the enzyme adenylyl cyclase, thus inhibiting its activity. Formation of Ca^{II}-bridged mixed complex can be visualised in the light of the results of the present investigation, which show that isoprenaline molecule acts as a bidentate ligand during chelation with metal(II) ions resulting in formation of ML and ML₂ complexes. Thus maximum four-coordination sites (out of six) of the metal ions are utilised and the remaining two positions (at least) are presumably used in the metal-enzyme bonding. When the drug is converted during metabolism to noradrenaline (an active pressure hormone) powerful cardiac stimulant action results⁶, Mg^{II} bound noradrenaline- α -receptor chelate¹⁰ increases the activity of adenylyl cyclase resulting in increase in concentration of the intracellular cyclic-AMP (AMP acts inside the cell and alters the cellular function).

Thus the selective and competitive bronchio-dilator activity of the drug may be explained due to presence of *N*-isopropyl-substitution in the basic noradrenaline structure (Fig. 1) as predicted by Mclean¹⁰. This may be due to its high basicity¹¹, as this substitution will increase the basicity of the molecule and result in formation of stable chelate with isoprenaline. Further, as Wells¹² has pointed out that the formation of a strain-free chelate ring may be involved or possibly even required for superior antihistaminic activity. The results of the present investigation clearly indicate formation of a five-membered chelate ring with the metal ions (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Metal chelate.

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